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AN ANALYTICAL STUDY ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF CONSUMERS TOWARDS INVESTMENT AVENUES

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Abstract

In Recent years, the huge increase in investment of the money has been seeing. There are various options available in the market for the investors. Consumers behave in not the same way for different products and services. This research paper explains the causes affecting the choice of investors and the consumers behave to invest their money in various investment options. The success or failure of an investment depends on the right approach to invest. This paper examines about the awareness of the consumers towards investment. This paper also explains how the preferences of unlike consumers are different for the several investment options.

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INTRODUCTION

Investment is the commitment of money or capital to purchase financial instruments or other assets in order to gain profitable returns in the form of interest, income, or appreciation of the value of the instrument. In the field of financial Management, investment is depositing money into an asset with the expectation of capital rise, dividends, and/or interest earnings. Investments are often made indirectly through intermediaries, such as banks, brokers, and insurance companies.

Consumers invest the money for the purpose of Safety of Principal, Income Stability, Authenticity and Freedom from Care, Tax Benefits etc. The different types of investments also cater to the two levels of risk tolerance: high risk and low risk. The potential consumers often have difficulties to identify differences between a financial product and other products.

Overseas investors are looking at India as an attractive investment destination owing to the prospects of high returns. A number of Corporate and Multi-National Companies from all over the world have established business in India and have expanded over the years.

Nowadays there is large number of investment tools available for e.g. Share market, Bank deposits, Mutual funds and bonds, Insurance sector, Real Estate etc. Every individual has different reasons for investing his/her money. Some like to invest in Share market because of high liquidity and high return, while exactly opposite to are those persons who thinks that share market is the most risky tool to invest their money. The real measure of investment success is meeting one's goal; investors will be winner if they can ensure the right investment for themselves, their family and their financial goal. The present study determines whether various factors influenced the preferences of investors towards investment schemes.

Review of Literature

According to Barber & Odean, University of California (2011), "The investors who inhabit the real world and those who populate academic models are distant cousins. Investors hold well-diversified portfolios and trade infrequently to minimize taxes and other investment costs. In practice, investors behave differently.

They trade frequently and have perverse stock selection ability, incurring unnecessary investment costs and return losses. They tend to sell their winners and hold their losers, generating unnecessary tax liabilities. Many hold poorly diversified portfolios, resulting in unnecessarily high levels of diversifiable risk, and many are unduly influenced by media and experiences. Individual investors who ignore the prescriptive advice to buy and hold low-fee, well-diversified portfolios, generally do so to their detriment.” According to Gallery and Gallery (2005), “Rational investors should hold diversified portfolios that include the most efficient combinations of assets to optimize risk and return, and which reflect investor utility preferences and time horizons.” As per the study conducted by SCMRD for Ministry of Company affairs (2004), “Majority of the retail investors do not regard mutual fund equity schemes as a superior investment compared to direct equity.”

The Institute of company secretaries of India in its Investor Education series III entitled, “Investment Decision making by a Lay Investor” (1991) explained the preconditions for investment decision making, analysis and evaluating risks. SEBI (1998) survey revealed that Risk appetite, investment

objective of the investor, income of the investor, funds available for investment, greatly influences the behavior of the investor in corporate securities at various levels. According to Brahmabhatt, Raghu & Malekar of Aruna Manharlal Shah Institute of Management and Research, Mumbai University (2012), “the awareness of investment knowledge, investment opportunities is quite high. Financial portals, financial news channels, financial newspapers help these people; various markets related T.V. shows, Expert talks, magazines. For Indian public money is everything. Therefore, they are more sensitive about their money. They will think hundred times before investing in any market and will expect more than that. They feel that they are having enough money, time, resources and opportunities with them for investing. Though they are having sound knowledge of financial market and economic condition of India yet they lack the edge above the others as this field is very unpredictable and vast hence they must be backed up by a financial planner.”

According to Petra, University of Hradec Králové (2012), “The insurance market in the Czech Republic on the supply side is exposed to pressure for higher commissions for insurance intermediaries and lower

margins calculated for the product. On the demand side, increasing demands for quality and service levels. One way to achieve higher profits is to gain knowledge capital from the consumer behavior. Aim of this document was to present a specific research plan implemented, which aimed to map the irrational behavior of consumer choice of insurance products. The results of the research project showed that most consumers under the influence of certain factors act irrationally. These factors include media coverage of the causes of claims discount, offer extension of insurance coverage.”

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of this study is to analyze the behaviour of consumers towards investment options, along with the following sub objectives:

- To study about the causes affecting the choice of investors.
- To learn about the awareness of the consumers regarding investment products

- To study about the preferences of individuals towards investments.

Research Methodology

Researcher took a sample of 200 respondents for the study. Respondents were the customers from different industries like real estates, insurance, financial services etc. Researcher used convenience-sampling technique for the collection of primary data. Primary data collected through a structured questionnaire having questions relevant to this study. Researcher focused on the valued customer through the questionnaire. The research location for the study was Jaipur & Dehradun city.

Analysis of Data

Chart 1: Age of Respondents

This chart shows the percentage of respondents with different age group. Maximum no. of respondents i.e. 32% belong to the age of less than 30 years. Only

14% of respondents are from the age group of above 50 years. 26% and 28% respondents are from the age group 30-40 years and 40-50 years respectively.

Chart 2: Income Level of Respondents

The above chart shows the percentage of respondents with different levels of income. Maximum no. of respondents i.e., 49% has their income lying in category upto 3 lakh

per annum. Few respondents i.e. 5% and 12% respondents have the income of above eight lakh and between 5-8 lakh respectively.

Chart 3: Occupation of Respondents

As per above chart, maximum no of respondents are of service class i.e. 65% of total respondents. Other respondents were from business class, retired persons, others (students) etc.

The chart 4 shows the awareness, knowledge and expertise of respondents

Chart 4: Investment Knowledge and Expertise

about the investment. Only few respondents, i.e. 9% of the respondents have much better investment knowledge and expertise for various products. Maximum no of respondents i.e., 39% respondents do not have the expertise and thorough knowledge about investment

According to chart 5 below, out of various investment avenue, insurance is most

preferred option as maximum no of respondents i.e., 42% respondents prefer it.

Chart 5: Preferred Investment Option

Chart 6: Income Invested By Respondents

This chart 6 shows that maximum no. of respondents, i.e., 39% prefer to invest 5% - 10% of their income and only 7%

respondents invest more than 25% of their income.

Chart 7: Sources Preferred by Respondents

On the basis of above chart, 51% of the respondents prefer to discuss with the professionals and consultants. Other

respondents have a preference of different sources like TV channels, newspapers, internet, family and friends' referrals etc.

Chart 8: Term of Investment Preferred

This chart 8 shows that most of the people prefer long term investment in order to meet their future requirements like education, marriage of their children, buying a house, old age needs etc. In this study, only 27% of the respondents prefer both the investment.

In the chart 9 , we can see that 36% of respondents have safety of funds as most important factor affecting their investment decision while 27%, have preferred tax saving over other factors.

Chart 9: Primary Objective of Investment

Chart 10: Organizations preferred by respondents

As above chart shows, 69% of respondents prefer to invest their money in government/public sector organizations, while others prefer private and foreign sector organizations.

Findings of the Study

Based on the analysis of data collected in Jaipur city and Dehradun city, researcher found various outcomes. The age and income of investors plays major role for taking decision towards the investment. Percentage of income, that persons invest, depends on their income. Persons, having

higher income, prefer to invest in real estates in place of insurance, mutual fund etc. Generally, persons from service class are interested for the investment in various options like insurance, mutual funds for securing their future. Business class persons prefer investment options like real estates. Most of the investors do not have knowledge about investment options. They also have less knowledge of managing their income and resources. They are interested to take advice from the investment consultants and experts. Persons give more attention towards security and safety while investing their money. They want to invest money in the schemes, which are safe and secure. Insurance is one of the best options that provide security, sure return on investment and life safety to the insurer. Most of the people normally invest minor portion of their earnings by having major expenses in their personal and family life. Having different life styles, persons have unlike needs. Most of the persons invest in long term schemes to get handsome return for the purpose of marriages, higher education of their children etc. Most of the persons invest in government organizations like banks, insurance, mutual funds shares etc. They have the perception that these organizations are reliable and stable for the investment.

Conclusion and Suggestions

The research paper has argued and examined a consumer behaviour surrounding substance in the light of data acquired from respondents on their buying and observing of investment options. The purpose of this study was to study the consumer investment behaviour for the products available in the market. Investors still do not want to invest money in the schemes where they find risk. Individual investors are more interested in the options where they may get maximum return without any risk. The type of investment products greatly influences the Consumers' investment behaviour. The paper has made an input to our existing knowledge and understanding of the important factors involved in buying different investment products. This research also describes that most of the consumers have less knowledge about investment products. Researcher wants to suggest that companies should provide proper and right information about the product and services to the customers. Companies should consider the age, income and other relevant factors to market their investment avenues to the prospects and existing customers. For human being, money is important for their life, so they are more sensitive about it. Persons think several times before investing

and expect more in return. People give more importance to savings and investments so marketers should avail this opportunity by providing appropriate options to them.

Scope for the future Research

The scope of the present study is limited because it focuses only on respondents of two famous cities as Jaipur and Dehradun in India. The results obtained may not be applicable to the country as a whole. However, there are many opportunities for the researcher to execute a similar study in different geographical locations of the country. This may also validate the research findings of the current research. Further research can also focus on the rural and urban population and study whether the opinion differs between them.

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